

Integrating Generative AI into Architectural Education: Insights on Design Strategies and Workflows

This work examines architecture students' engagement with Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), focusing on their perceptions, usage patterns, and emergent workflows. Through surveys and two structured workshops, the study identifies three main GenAI-driven design approaches—convergent “AI-rendering,” divergent “associative ideation,” and emergent “selective breeding”—each reflecting different levels of creative control. Findings reveal that while students view GenAI positively, they express concerns regarding authorship and experience challenges in controlling GenAI-driven design processes. Notable breakthroughs include the strategic use of textual and visual prompts to align outputs with design intent, as well as the creative use of unexpected results to drive exploration. The systematization and alignment of the identified GenAI-driven design strategies with specific design phases foster AI literacy, critical engagement, and visual thinking, positioning GenAI as an efficiency enabler, a meaningful complement to conventional design methods, and a catalyst for creative exploration in architectural education.

Keywords: *Generative Artificial Intelligence, Architectural Education and Pedagogy, Generative Design, Digital Technology Adoption in Architecture.*

1. Introduction

Advancements in Generative AI (GenAI) are impacting different social and professional sectors, including the practice and teaching of architecture. Diffusion models (DMs), including text-to-image, image-to-image, and a combination of the two, are becoming part of the architectural design toolkit. However, the accelerated proliferation and evolution of GenAI design tools contribute to a lack of shared literacy and established guidelines for their effective use. This gap may lead to the misapplication of such tools or hinder their broader adoption within architectural practice, which typically is slow in integrating technological innovation in the design process, as evidenced by the protracted transition from Computer-Aided Design (CAD) to Building Information Modeling (BIM) tools (Koutamanis et al. 2023; Borrmann et al. 2018) or the inconsistent adoption of parametric tools across various design phases (Kio and Mayer 2025).

Nevertheless, GenAI offers new capabilities in idea generation, visualization, and interactive design development, opportunities that architectural practice and education cannot overlook. Such tools are becoming increasingly used by architectural offices, academics, and students, influencing professional practices and educational settings in which future architects are trained. Education is key to circumventing misuse of GenAI tools and fostering a use that enhances human capabilities and creativity in architectural design. Thus, it is paramount to leverage GenAI and its future developments in architecture program curricula. However, given GenAI's novelty, it is necessary to effectively integrate GenAI into architecture curricula by first assessing its current use by students, identifying potential areas of application, and evaluating benefits, risks, gaps, and needs. Such a study will enable discussion about the successful integration of GenAI in architecture

teaching.

1.1. Research objectives

This study assesses architecture students' perceptions of GenAI across varying levels of proficiency, exploring how their familiarity and competence with digital design tools influence both their attitudes and practical engagement with GenAI. It examines how students integrate GenAI into various design tasks and the resulting design workflows that emerge, with a particular focus on the design phases, constraints, and tasks where the use of GenAI is most impactful. By examining these dynamics, the research aims to identify GenAI's capabilities as an enabler of creativity and/or design efficiency. To explore potential pedagogical avenues, the study maps the benefits, risks, gaps, and needs for seamlessly integrating GenAI into architectural teaching, positioning it as a human creativity and efficiency augments in architectural design processes.

2. State of the art

The emergence of GenAI in architecture results from decades of intertwined technical and cultural development. According to Steinfeld (2023), GenAI evolved through three phases: the foundational era in the mid-20th century, the early 2000s resurgence of machine learning, driven by big data and computational advances, and the recent wave of informal, community-led innovation. Steinfeld emphasizes that informal GenAI innovations, often led by self-taught technologists, have shaped today's generative architectural visual culture, redefining authorship and collaboration while raising cultural and ethical implications.

GenAI consists of statistical learning models trained on large datasets encoded as high-dimensional matrices known as embeddings (Koehler 2024a). Diffusion Models (DMs) use convolutional neural networks to gradually add noise to images (forward diffusion or noising) during training and then learn to reverse this process by reconstructing the original image (reverse diffusion or denoising). This process occurs in latent space, a compressed and abstract lower-dimensional representation of image features (e.g., a vector). Once trained, DMs generate images by iteratively denoising random noise to produce a coherent image aligned with a given prompt (Rombach et al. 2022; Ho, Jain, and Abbeel 2020).

Koehler (2024a) describes DMs' latent space as a conceptual design space, enabling the exploration of variations and analogies across multiple dimensions, such as texture, form, or spatial relationships. Additionally, similarities between DMs and architectural thinking mechanisms — namely, analogy, spatial association, and ambiguity — support variability in generative design workflows and knowledge extraction (Koehler 2024a). In that regard, Koehler investigated GenAI's ability to understand and recompose architectural forms in context-sensitive ways in two studies (Koehler 2023; 2024b). In one study, the author used GenAI to generate synthetic architectures, i.e., novel spatial compositions that synthesize diverse typologies and features (Koehler 2023); in another, GenAI analyzed and synthesized diverse architectural typologies to infer their embodied carbon based on visual features, such as materials and building parts (Koehler 2024b). Despite limitations regarding accuracy and model bias, both studies show GenAI's potential to provide new architectural insights and enhance analysis, creative tasks, and critical thinking, positioning GenAI as a collaborative, not replacement, tool.

Kudless (2024) proposes GenAI as a collaborator that thrives on ambiguity, contradiction, and imperfection. By using unconventional prompts or image inputs, architects can push GenAI beyond default settings to unlock new design possibilities and reclaim creative freedom in a field often constrained by coherence and efficiency. GenAI becomes a partner in the messy, iterative, and often nonsensical early stages of design, where ambiguity and contradiction can foster innovation.

Nevertheless, GenAI presents several challenges, including high computational, economic, and environmental costs, a lack of domain-specific training data, and limited representation of project-specific needs, as it primarily targets visual style over design constraints. Additional concerns include low AI and data literacy among architects, as well as GenAI's inability to generate outputs based on intentional design logic due to its statistical nature (Koehler 2024a). Kudless (2023) identifies three main biases: (i) collective biases from English- and Western-centric training datasets, (ii) computational biases that result from developers' preferences, and (iii) users' cognitive biases introduced by prompts and image selection. These biases influence outputs, often reinforcing dominant cultural narratives and aesthetic norms. While GenAI offers creative potential, it risks narrowing architectural discourse without critical engagement with its underlying assumptions and limitations.

Other authors have investigated the use of GenAI in design practice through empirical studies. Wadinambiarachchi et al. (2024) conducted a between-subjects experiment to assess the impact of GenAI on visual creative tasks. They found that using GenAI as an inspiration tool for sketching led to significantly higher design fixation (i.e., the narrowing of creative exploration based on AI suggestions) and reduced the originality and variety of sketches produced by participants compared to using Google Image Search or no inspiration at all. Prompt repetition based on the design brief and the close imitation of AI outputs (fixation displacement) explain these findings. The study suggests that while GenAI can aid creativity, it may also constrain it unless paired with strategies that encourage divergent thinking and avoid fixation.

Tang et al. (2024) explored GenAI in industrial design education, proposing a framework with two phases: Pre-AI (divergent, human-driven ideation) and Post-AI (convergent, AI-assisted refinement). Through two case studies involving students, the authors showed that GenAI can enhance creativity and efficiency while preserving core design skills, critical thinking, and ethical awareness. However, students also faced challenges, including design fixation, overreliance on AI-generated outputs, technical barriers (e.g., AI literacy, prompt crafting), and ethical concerns (e.g., bias, originality, and authorship). Nevertheless, many intend to use GenAI in future projects. The authors concluded that despite GenAI's benefits, human intuition, critical thinking and foundational design skills remain essential, especially in early design stages, thus advocating for a balanced integration of GenAI in design education.

In sum, while GenAI holds transformative potential as a collaborative design tool, its current use often reinforces aesthetic conformity and cultural bias (Kudless 2024). To avoid narrowing architectural discourse, it is crucial to examine how architects perceive and engage with GenAI. Insights into their experiences can inform strategies that foster AI literacy, divergent thinking, and ethical awareness, encouraging GenAI-supported creative and context-sensitive design practices.

3. Methods

To explore how architecture students, at different stages of their academic program, use GenAI across various design tasks and phases, the study implemented two within-subjects experiments. These experiments aim to assess students' perceptions of GenAI, examine its impact on their design workflows, and identify gaps, needs, and usage patterns. In both experiments, students completed a two-stage survey and reported the results, workflow, and design solutions on a MIRO board. We observed the progress of the experiments and concluded them with a review session of the students' work, which included an open discussion. Additionally, after the experiments, we conducted a post-critical reflection on the observations collected during the experiments and the results that they produced. Adobe Firefly was the GenAI design tool chosen due to its capability to utilize and combine text-to-image and image-to-image AI approaches, as well as its better ability to enhance, edit, and refine sketches produced by users or synthetically generated when compared with other GenAI tools such as DALL-E and Midjourney (Balasubramanian and Periyaswamy 2025).

3.1 Design of experiments

Experiment #1 consisted of a one-day GenAI workshop to support initial visual ideation for a graduated architecture studio class. The studio project asked students to transform Sydhavnskvarteret, the southern part of Aarhus's east port (Denmark), with a focus on reusing on-site existing buildings and materials (see Figure 1). The workshop involved 38 participants and consisted of designing a sculptural pavilion using on-site architectural and material references that the students had to compile. First, the students completed the exercise using only conventional methods (e.g., sketches, photomontages, 3D modeling, and rendering). They then completed the same exercise using only GenAI. The purpose was to compare both methods in terms of fostering architectural ideation.

Experiment #2 was another one-day workshop designed to support an undergraduate architecture studio. The studio consisted of designing an office building at Jyllandsgadekvarteret in Aalborg (Denmark), focusing on user requirements, energy efficiency, and indoor environmental quality (see Figure 1). The workshop included 28 participants and followed a similar structure to Experiment #1 but with a more focused and defined design task. Since the students were further along in their studio projects, the activity centered specifically on exploring different façade concepts and compositions. At the end of the session, a group discussion provided an opportunity to reflect critically on both the process and outcomes.

In both experiments, participants needed to report and reflect on their design process, including registering workflows, procedural sequences of using and mixing different design methods, key prompts, and any insightful realizations.

Figure 1. Sites of the two experiments. Left: Experiment 1, Sydhavnskvarteret in Aarhus, Denmark. Right: Experiment 2, Jyllandsgadekvarteret in Aalborg, Denmark.

3.2 Survey

Both experiments shared an online participant survey with two distinct parts, a pre- and a post-experiment questionnaire. The participants completed the pre-experiment questionnaire before beginning the workshop's design tasks. The questionnaire focused on students' literacy with digital tools used in architectural design processes, knowledge about GenAI tools, use of GenAI in architectural design, GenAI engagement and receptivity, and thoughts and concerns about GenAI integration in architectural practice.

After the workshops, participants answered the post-experiment questionnaire, which focused on three aspects related to GenAI use:

1. *Learning curve and skill development*, which included questions related to the difficulty of using GenAI in a meaningful way, its ability to support architectural design processes, and the challenges of learning and applying GenAI.
2. *Design process*, which compared GenAI with conventional design methods in supporting ideation, inquired about the types of creative processes associated with GenAI (i.e., erratic or non-erratic) and experienced level of limitation while using GenAI.
3. *Perception and intention*, which aim to assess the perceived ownership, authorship, and control of the design process and outcomes, as well as participants' intention to use GenAI in future projects. The post-experiment questionnaire concludes with the same question about engagement in using GenAI as the pre-experiment questionnaire to evaluate whether participants' initial expectations about the technology were reinforced or altered by their experience.

Both parts of the survey included open-ended questions to capture descriptive feedback and closed-ended questions to quantify and qualify the different aspects of the experiments. Most of the closed-ended questions used a five-point Likert-scale that ranges from 1 to 5, where 3 represents the intermediate or neutral value for the specific question. The authors critically analyzed the

descriptive answers to identify trends and patterns and processed quantitative data using simple statistics and various data visualizations.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Survey results

Figures 2 to 6 show the survey results. Figures 2, 3, and 4 are from the pre-experiment questionnaire, while Figures 5 and 6 are from the post-experiment survey. Figure 2 portrays the participant's level of proficiency with digital design tools. Most participants reported a good level of digital design skills, with 85% of graduate students in Experiment #1 and 82% of undergraduates in Experiment #2 rating themselves as intermediate (level 3) or proficient (level 4).

Figure 2. Participants' proficiency with digital design tools.

Figure 3. GenAI tools previously used by the participants.

Additionally, Figure 3 shows that the participants are well aware of GenAI, considering the wide range of GenAI tools listed. The most used are ChatGPT, followed by Adobe Firefly. Excluding these, the groups drift in terms of tools used. Graduate students tend to list more established tools, such as Midjourney and Dall-E, while undergraduate students list more tools with a particular emphasis on GenAI tools for animation and architectural visualization, such as Rendair AI or Sora. Although graduate students are only two years ahead of undergraduates, the younger students are more curious to explore different GenAI.

Figure 4 shows that both groups have similar GenAI utilization patterns. Most participants reported using it occasionally, with 63% in Experiment 1 and 59% in Experiment 2. Around 16–18% said they only know about the technology, 15–16% use it frequently, and 6–8% are frequent users and enthusiasts. Regarding GenAI application, the participants split their answers between ideation (41–47%) and visualization and design refinement (47–48%).

Figure 4. GenAI usage and engagement patterns among participants.

The pre-experiment questionnaire ended by asking the participants to share their thoughts and concerns about GenAI in architecture. Both groups shared similar views. Most see GenAI as a helpful tool for saving time on repetitive tasks. Many also view it as useful for generating ideas, quick sketches, and testing materials. However, concerns exist about job displacement, authorship uncertainty, professional responsibility, and technological regulation. Some worry that AI could make designs too generic and hamper creativity. Others felt the technology relies too much on user input or outdated data and, thus, still needs improvement.

Figure 5 shows GenAI’s receptivity ratings before and after the experiments using a 1–5 Likert-scale. Both groups have a moderate (3) to moderately high (4) reception. For graduate students in Experiment #1, using GenAI during the workshop did not change their views. However, undergraduate students in Experiment #2 showed a slight increase in acceptance, suggesting that regular use might favor GenAI adoption.

Figure 5. Participant receptivity to GenAI before and after the experiments.

Figure 6 reveals how participants perceived the use of GenAI in assisting with design tasks during both experiments. Most found it moderately easy to learn and use. However, for 25% of graduate students in Experiment #1 it was difficult to learn. Undergraduate students generally found it easier to learn and use GenAI to produce meaningful results. This trend is also evident in how each group viewed GenAI's ability to support the design process.

Both groups had similar views on the design process. They showed mixed feelings about GenAI's creative support compared to conventional methods, suggesting a need for both. Graduate students in Experiment #1 slightly preferred conventional approaches. Overall, participants felt GenAI encouraged more erratic idea generation. Regarding limitations, responses varied, but graduate students reported more challenges than undergraduates. Most limitations were related to control, as participants struggled to adjust specific parts of a design, manage changes across design iterations, avoid the unwanted generation of elements like trees or furniture, and clearly express their ideas through prompts.

Participants felt their authorship diminished when using GenAI, with graduate students experiencing this more strongly. Views on control of the design process with GenAI were mixed—38-43% rated it low (2), and 39-41% rated it moderate (3). Despite these concerns, most participants expressed moderate to high interest in using GenAI in future projects, supporting the idea of incorporating it into architecture education.

When asked to reflect on their experience, many participants noted the importance of precise prompt wording, as minor changes could significantly affect the output. They also found that using reference images or base sketches helped align results with their design intent. Some participants found GenAI helpful in materials and 'stylistic' exploration in early design stages. Others discovered that refining designs step-by-step or regenerating specific areas improved outcomes. Some appreciated the unexpected results, which often sparked new and creative ideas. In contrast, others admitted that they were easily drawn to visually appealing GenAI outputs, often becoming fixated on them.

Figure 6. Post-experiment questionnaire results: GenAI skill development, integration in design, and user perceptions about its use.

4.2 GenAI Design Workshop Results

In both experiments, participants used a shared Miro board to track and document their design processes. Based on the Miro boards graphical data and the joint discussion rounds at the end of each experiment, the study identifies three different AI-driven design approaches: (1) the convergent “AI-rendering,” (2) the divergent “associative ideation,” and (3) the emergent “selective breeding.” The following defines and exemplifies each of these design approaches.

The convergent “AI-rendering” approach is a highly controlled design process where the designer operates with a clear, predefined vision of the desired outcome. In this context, GenAI serves as a targeted tool to search for and visualize a preconceived idea – similar to conventional analog or digital rendering techniques that materialize an image already formed in the designer’s mind. Figure 7 illustrates this approach, reflecting a linear process that uses GenAI to deliberately visualize a pavilion placed within the specific context of the design assignment.

Figure 7. Example of a graduate student’s work that aligns with the convergent “AI-rendering” approach. The design process depicts a very linear, deliberate, and visualization-focused approach.

The divergent “associative ideation” approach emerged as the most used strategy in students’ AI-driven design explorations. This approach involves an open-ended search for design alternatives, characterized by a continuous “what if?” mindset. It supports an iterative design process where students explore design problems and solutions in parallel, enabling broad and creative experimentation. As shown in the work of undergraduate and graduate students, depicted in Figures 8 and 9, respectively, it leverages GenAI’s ability to associate user inputs, such as text prompts, composition references, and style references, with visual features from existing image content. Its successful application depends on users’ ability to continue the associative ideation process based on AI-generated outputs. Although not directly visible in the students’ submitted work, observations during the experiments and insights from final group discussions revealed that the students’ creative-cognitive responses to AI outputs are crucial to effectively applying this method. Ultimately, this approach supports combinational creativity (Boden 2004), enabling design processes in which the combination of existing ideas, references, knowledge, and experiences drives the generation of new solutions.

Figure 8. Depiction of an undergraduate student work showing an iterative AI-driven design process that aligns with the proposed “*associative ideation*” approach. In this example, the student has used hand-drawn sketches as composition references, together with text prompts, to control and direct the generation of AI image outputs.

Figure 9. Example of an undergraduate student work showcasing the divergent “*associative ideation*” approach. With the assignment of designing an office building for the company Bang & Olufsen (B&O), the student initiated and directed the process by using a hand drawing as composition reference and a picture of a B&O retail store as the style reference.

Figure 10. Example of a graduate student work showing an emergent AI-driven design process that aligns with the proposed “*selective breeding*” approach in which desired aspects/traits are selected by and fed into the next generation of images either as composition or style reference.

The emergent “selective breeding” approach is the last of the identified representative design workflows. Unlike the “associative ideation” approach, which involves continuous iteration between new user input and AI-based generation of new visual output with varying levels of directionality, this approach employs a more selective process. As Figure 10 illustrates, the student began with a prompt, similar to “associative ideation,” but then selectively chose the most promising AI-generated image output and used it as a composition reference for the next generation of outputs in Adobe Firefly. By repeating this emergent process of selecting desired traits and breeding them into subsequent image generations or “offsprings,” this approach allows students to guide the ideation process while remaining open to unexpected outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study examined how architecture students engage with Generative AI (GenAI) tools in architectural education, revealing both the potential and challenges of integrating them into architectural workflows. Through a comprehensive survey and two structured workshops, we mapped students’ perceptions, insights, and experienced benefits and limitations as well as identified three distinct GenAI-driven design approaches—convergent “AI-rendering,” divergent “associative ideation,” and emergent “selective breeding”—each reflecting varying degrees of creative control and different opportunities for integration in architectural design workflows.

We observed that students generally held an optimistic yet cautious view of GenAI in architecture. Most were moderately engaged with GenAI, using it primarily for ideation and visualization. Their concerns are mainly ethical and echo those identified in the literature (Tang, Windham, and Bush 2024) , including the lack of regulation for GenAI, potential job displacement, and unclear authorship. The combination of precise prompts with reference images or sketches to better align outputs with design intent and support convergent workflows was the main reported insightful breakthrough. Students also recognized the creative potential of unexpected results as drivers for divergent and emergent design approaches. However, limitations were also evident. Students struggled with controlling specific design elements, articulating ideas through prompts, and maintaining a sense of authorship. While some became overly influenced by visually appealing outputs, others recognized the importance of critical engagement, highlighting the need for guided integration of GenAI into design education.

The pedagogical integration of GenAI should foster collaborative design processes to reframe perceptions about ambiguous authorship by enhancing the ability to maintain control over the design process. To support effective use of GenAI, students should learn both textual and visual prompt crafting, engage in critical feedback exercises—from open-ended explorations to more focused conceptual tasks—and receive guidance in using GenAI to support iterative design development. Additionally, it is necessary to reinforce and expand students’ visual culture, especially on data visualization, to avoid uncritical design fixation on visually appealing outputs and to help students use GenAI feedback more effectively in developing spatial narratives within contextual design tasks. These strategies build upon existing pedagogical and disciplinary practices, such as drawing, by integrating them with GenAI to enhance architectural design processes. Notably, some participants highlighted how the quality of visual prompts influenced GenAI outputs.

Despite GenAI's limitations, the experiments showed that in open-ended, exploratory contexts, it can effectively foster combinational creativity and support iterative, reflective design processes. Students who adopted associative and emergent workflows were better able to engage GenAI as a co-creative partner rather than relying on it as a deterministic tool.

Educators should align GenAI-driven design approaches with various design phases by providing examples and tutorials. The convergent “AI rendering” approach is more effective in the refinement and later design phases, where users have a clearer understanding of their goals. However, students can still use this approach as an exploratory tool, particularly in material selection studies. The divergent “associative ideation” approach suits early conceptual phases, encouraging open-ended exploration and combinational creativity by blending diverse ideas and references. The selective and recursive nature of the emergent “selective breeding” supports evolutionary-like design processes by enabling students to generate different design solutions and combine selected features to evolve and refine design variations while remaining open to unexpected outputs. This approach fits early design development phases that require more controlled and guided exploration or refinement.

In conclusion, to leverage GenAI’s potential in architectural education, it should be integrated as a complementary method to conventional design methods. Educators should emphasize AI literacy, critical engagement with AI outputs, and strategies to mitigate design fixation. Based on the identified GenAI-driven design approaches, future architectural curricula should frame GenAI not only as an efficiency enabler but as a critical augmentation tool for human creativity. Since both experiments were limited to one-day workshops, the findings may not be fully generalizable. To address this, future research will replicate this study in extended three-week studio settings. While this investigation focused on visual and stylistic explorations, future work will integrate GenAI-driven design with other AI approaches, particularly those used in performance-based design, including surrogate modeling and optimization techniques.

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